

How to choose your perfect Biobank Information Management System

Definition BIMS vs. LIMS

1. Former Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) for specimen/tube/freezer have evolved towards more patient-centric Biobank Information Management Systems (BIMS).
2. Management of the complete life cycle of biological samples and their associated data.
3. Improve operations, standardise data collections, optimises sample information and management while complying with standards and regulations.
4. Manage patient clinical information, consent, analytical results, batch work and integration with robotics or medical software.

The BIMS-Matrix

Describe your biobank

- How many direct employees does your biobank have (how many of them IT experts)? How many external clients (researcher, clinicians...) would you need to accommodate?
- How many collections/ sample types/ storage possibilities (storage capacity, space, temperature) would you need to cover?
- Which technologies services does the biobank offer except for storage (tissue sectioning, slice staining, DNA/ RNA-extraction, further analytics...)? Would that information need to be covered by the BIMS? #provenance
- Is your biobank part of a bigger institution? Which interfaces are needed (clinical information, external projects, networks)?

About the BIMS provider + software

- Since when is the company in this line of business? What is the background?
- How big is the company (personnel)? #Sustainability #Capacity #Scaling
- Commercial? #Costs
- Start-up? #Flexibility
- National or international localisation of the company headquarters? #Compliance #Language
- Costs for: Licence, installation, maintenance, training
- Different contract options? Service? Licence only? Development partnership?
- Operations: Backup strategy/ stability, support/ sustainability, supported database technologies?
- General security and data protection? Is the BIMS conforming to GDPR?
- How quick will specific requests be handled? (Support-workflow, ticketing system, personnel)?

General usage

- Which (3) main workflows/ processes would you need the BIMS to cover (sample registration, tissue section cuttings,..)?
- Would training for the lab personnel be in your language or in English?
- How intuitive is the UI/ UX in comparison to other providers?
- Is or can the frontend be browser based?
- Would it be possible to answer external sample/ project requests directly via the BIMS (sample search like in the Locator)?
- How about vendor-lock? Would it be easily possible to migrate the stored information, if you decide to change the system?
- Can you use the BIMS to provide you with analyses/ statistics (KPIs, how many samples, how many projects...)?
- Questions that might come from the institution's side (HR,...): Possibility of misuse for working time tracking? Energy efficiency? Certificates?

Operations

- Does the rights management fit with the roles in your biobank/ institution? Can several different clients (technicians, researchers, clinicians, biobank responsible) with different modes of access (manage, edit, read only,...) be managed?
- Are the given workflows mirroring your processes? Alternatively, how easily can they be adapted? With/ without additional costs/ proprietary IT dev resources?
- Do you have IT personnel within your biobank, which could take care of administration or even further development of the BIMS? If not, is the institution's IT personnel capable/ willing to support the system?
- Is a Single Sign-On via your clinical information system's authentication possible?
- Versioning possible (Audit-trail)?
- Compatibility with other systems/ data sources/ standards:
 - HL7 FHIR or ODSEasy interface?
 - Interface with your clinical information system?
 - Export/ import via XPS, CSV, XML possible?
 - REST-API?
 - Interfaces for other biobank internal lab equipment (rack scanner, pipetting robot, automated storage,...)

Extras

- Open Source licensing? General access to the code for proprietary development?
- Management of clinical trials (including ECRF)? Additional modules available? Coasts!
- DIN EN ISO 13485:2016 Medical Devices or any other certificates
- Accounting module for the biobank?

Exemplary software providers

In use within the German Biobank Alliance

We (germanbiobanknode@charite.de) could offer contacts within the GBA, if you have specific questions:

- <https://www.kairos.de/produkte/centraxx/> (now owned by IQVia)
- <https://www.starlims.com/de/>
- <https://www.bitcare.de/>
- <https://www.informeleon.de/>
- <https://www.openspecimen.org/>

Other providers

We can offer contact to the providers only:

- <https://henry.idcohorts.net/de/>
- <https://swissdidata.com/>

Literature

- <https://zenodo.org/record/4723753#.Y0gYbC7P2Uk>
- <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36201224/>
- https://www.liebertpub.com/doi/10.1089/bio.2022.0076?utm_source=Adestra&utm_medium=email&utm_term=&utm_content=Article1-OA&utm_campaign=BIO%20FP%20October%2019%2C%202022